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CDIO OPERATION EDUCATION THROUGH REGIONAL COLLABORATION

Mikiko Sode Tanaka¹
International College of Technology
Kanazawa, Japan

Takao Ito²
Kanazawa Institute of Technology
Nonoichi, Japan

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ABSTRACT

CDIO, a concept devised by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and three universities from Sweden, stands for “conceive, design, implement, and operate.” The goal of CDIO education is to enable students to lead in the creation and operation of new products, processes, and systems. Several studies have been conducted on CDIO education, but there is little discussion on operation education. Therefore, here we focused on the operation education method and explain CDIO operation education through regional collaboration using a bus location system through a Web application. In addition, we explain its results and educational significance.

In CDIO education, operation is defined as the lifecycle support and evolution. During this phase, the system is managed so that it can be operated without troubles, finding and improving system problems, and considering the next expansion. In our study, students learned the system operation and maintenance by operating a bus location system. In addition, they learned how to operate the system steadily by responding to accidents such as bus breakdowns and replacement by new bus purchases.

Operation education faces the issue of how to deal with sudden problems. It is not suitable for a curricular course because it is impossible to predict troubles, and it is impossible to create a plan. However, with this trouble, there is also an opportunity to teach the important parts of a system. It can be said that this is the most important part of education that enables students to create a system to earn money.

¹ *Mikiko Sode Tanaka*

sode@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

² *Ito Takao*

ito@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 CDIO education in regular classes

There is a growing mismatch between universities on one side and society and industry on the other. Furthermore, there is a need for human resources that could flexibly respond to changes and create a new value. CDIO is a concept devised by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and three universities from Sweden to respond to this reform of engineering education. CDIO stands for “conceive, design, implement, and operate,” and it is called the “CDIO Initiative,” which consists of the CDIO syllabus and the CDIO standard. It aims for high-quality education through the framework using real-world systems and products [1].

Our school has implemented CDIO education since 2010. At first, it was introduced in the Design Project course (PD), which are regular classes [2, 3]. Figure 1 shows the educational curriculum. Our school identifies five stages of engineering design processes. PD1 is a curriculum intended for learning problem discovery, problem clarification, and idea creation; and PD2 is a curriculum intended for learning idea creation, idea evaluation and careful selection, and concrete implementation of ideas. By evaluating PD education at our school from a CDIO perspective, we found that it corresponds to C (conceive) and D (design).

Fig. 1. Relationship between the Engineering Curriculum and CDIO Education

1.2 CDIO education in extracurricular classes

In the regular curriculum, it is difficult to have appropriate project activities and meaningful experiences due to the limited class time and the obligation to evaluate academic ability. For example, students need to understand practical requirements analysis, system design, architecture design, and system construction to build an information and communication technology system. These concepts can be learned in regular classes, but this alone does not make them capable of creating a system. To learn how to design a highly useful system, students actually need to perform requirement analysis and system design. For example, students must experience

failure due to many omissions in requirement analysis and inability to create a system design. Otherwise, students were able to build the system, but when users tried to use it, the system did not work properly, and students had to recreate it. It is impossible to create a system without accumulating the kind of experience mentioned above. It is difficult to reflect these experiences in the syllabus and grade evaluation, and it is difficult to adopt them as regular classes. Therefore, International College of Technology (ICT) and Kanazawa Institute of Technology (KIT) have given this role to extracurricular activities. Extracurricular classes play an important role in strengthening interdisciplinary education in marketing, sales, electric/electronic circuits, programming, security, art, and so forth through the process of problem solving [4, 5, 6].

Figure 2 shows the processes of setting goals for activities to attract tourists to Ishikawa Prefecture, which was carried out by a group of students as an extracurricular class. Education through extracurricular classes is effective because students can set and execute their own goals using ideas freely without being restricted by time. It also provides the advantage of being able to perform all phases of CDIO education. However, these activities did not include long-term operations.

Fig. 2. Determining project activity contents using the GROW model

2 WEB VERSION OF THE BUS LOCATION INFORMATION DISPLAY SYSTEM

2.1 Configuration of the bus location system

Extracurricular classes have been held with the keyword of citizen support, and this activity started in 2015. Approximately 50 students participate every year. These classes are mainly working on information and communication technology at bus stops,

and students have developed a system that allows a bus user to check the location of the bus on the WEB. Figure 3 shows the overall configuration of the bus location system developed by students. The bus is equipped with the Global Positioning System, and the location is uploaded to the cloud using lot Sim or LoRa. The system allows users to check the bus location on their mobile devices, on the Web, or at tablet-terminal-type bus stops. The tablet-terminal-type bus stops are equipped with a tablet, so one can check the bus location and timetable.

As a result of several demo questionnaire surveys, there was a request to continue using the bus location system, so the students started intermittent operation in 2018 and actual operation in 2020. This is the beginning of P: operation education in CDIO education.

Fig. 3. Bus location system configuration

2.2 Operation education

A questionnaire survey revealed that there were many requests from citizens to continue using the system; thus, students started operation continuously in April 2020. The bus location system that informs the location of the bus was named “Notty bus doko.” There are two main jobs for students in operations:

1. Check whether the bus location system is working without stopping.
2. Update the system according to the revision of the bus time twice a year.

To operate the bus location system, students created a technique to judge whether the system worked properly, and thus avoided constant monitoring. The bus position is updated to the cloud 10 times per second, and if data are not uploaded to the cloud for a few minutes, an email will be sent to all members. As students have to be able to respond even if a breakdown occurs during class, they decided to consider the procedure for identifying the cause in advance and take corrective action. The city official contacted one of the students about the change of bus time one month before; therefore, we decided to consult with the group and create a plan.

Here, we will explain the failure cases in the operation (Figures 4 and 5). The location of the bus is no longer uploaded to the cloud, and the bus driver has informed us that the equipment installed on the bus is not turning on. The student went to the bus operating company, confirmed that the fuse was broken, and collected it. Figure 4 shows the power supply part of the bus location system installed in bus by students, and Figure 5 shows the broken fuse collected by students. The next morning, one of the students received a message from the bus operator that the wiper of the bus did not work. Students had no idea what caused it. The investigation revealed that the power supply position of the fuse collected by the student was also used for the wiper. From these failures, students considered countermeasures. They decided to create a manual and operate it. The following is part of the manual:

1. When installing the device, avoid places that share it with other functions.
2. Be sure to have a replacement fuse and replace it instead of simply collecting the broken fuse.

Fig. 4. Power supply installed on the bus

Fig. 5. Broken fuse

Fig. 6. Web version of bus location information display system

As we continued to use it, we began to want to make the system compatible with routes that the bus location system did not yet support; consequently, we responded to routes extending to other cities and released it. In addition, changes in student consciousness and in the adults began to take a positive direction; for example, a bus driver asked the students to create a bus management system for bus drivers. Since the beginning of 2021, we have been working on the development of a system that supports COVID-19 countermeasures, counts the number of passengers on the bus, and informs the users. Figure 6 shows the Web version of the bus location information display system.

3 EVALUATION RESULTS BY CDIO EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION CRITERIA

In KIT and ICT, Parts 1 and 2 of the CDIO syllabus (see Table 1) are taught as regular classes, and Parts 3 and 4 are taught as extracurricular activities. In extracurricular activities, the project system is adopted, the project is managed by the students, the teachers only give guidance by the coaching method, and the students decide the management method and manage it. Students can learn Parts 3 and 4 of the CDIO syllabus through project activity in regional collaboration.

Table 1. CDIO Syllabus V2.0 [1]

1	Disciplinary knowledge and reasoning
2	Personal and professional skills and attributes
3	Interpersonal skills: Teamwork and communication
4	Conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating systems in the enterprise, social, and environmental context: The innovation process

We evaluated the operation of the system project of the bus location system according to the CDIO syllabus evaluation criteria. Fine-grain details of the third level of the CDIO syllabus V2.0 are Forming Effective Teams, Team Operation, Team Growth and Evolution, Team Leadership, and Technical and Multidisciplinary Teaming. Our project-based education covers all third-level items. Students are recruiting and educating project participants, as well as developing and operating the system in cooperation with city officials and bus companies. With each passing year, the number of project members has increased; further, as the number of jobs that can be accomplished has increased, the number of functions of the systems we provide has also increased. With the support of the members of the graduated project, the chances of learning have increased to a great extent have increased.

The students were able to design, build, and operate the system that could actually be managed considering the business aspect. Therefore, the students were able to learn all the items of Level 4 of CDIO Syllabus V2.0. Table 2 shows Part 4.6 Operation. After

experiencing mistakes several times, students could successfully complete all aspects of Part 4.6 except for 4.6.5 (Disposal and Life-End Issues).

Table 2. Part 4.6 of CDIO Syllabus V2.0 [1, 7]

4.6.1	Designing and Optimizing Sustainable and Safe Operation
4.6.2	Training and Operations
4.6.3	Supporting the System Life Cycle
4.6.4	System Improvement and Evolution
4.6.5	Disposal and Life-End Issues
4.6.6	Operations Management

We evaluated students' activity using the evaluation criteria for CDIO syllabus Part 4. Table 3 shows the evaluation criteria for CDIO syllabus Part 4. This activity is not a regular class but an extracurricular activity, and the students who participated did so on their own initiative. In addition, the students was able to take charge of the job decided within the team and accomplish it. In addition, the results were regularly explained to the person in charge of the city, and future plans were also discussed. Furthermore, some of the results were published as one treatise [8, 9]. Through the activities, he learned software and hardware technology and succeeded in operating a system that informs the location of buses that make the lives of citizens convenient. It can be said that the evaluation items of Part 4 were fully satisfied.

Table 3. Evaluation Criteria for CDIO Syllabus Part 4 [1, 7]

1	To have been exposed to
2	To be able to participate and contribute
3	To be able to understand and explain
4	To be skilled in the practice or implementation
5	To be able to lead or innovate

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In CDIO education, operation is defined as life cycle support and evolution. In this paper, we focused on the operation education method and explained CDIO Operation education through regional collaboration by using the bus location system through a WEB application. We explained the results and the educational significance of operation education. This was achieved through extracurricular activities. We chose extracurricular activities considering available time and evaluation.

Operation is the phase of managing the system so that it can be operated without trouble, finding and improving system problems, and considering the next expansion. Students learned how to operate the system steadily by responding to accidents such as bus breakdowns and replacement by new bus purchases.

Operation education faces the difficulty of deciding how to deal with sudden problems. It is not suitable for a curricular course because it is impossible to predict, and it is not possible to create a plan. However, there is also an opportunity to teach the important parts of the system. It can be said that this is the most important part of education that enables students to create a system to earn money. The activities introduced this time follow the CDIO educational philosophy of learning from practice. Students solved the problem by using Information and Communication Technology. The system is still in function. We believe the students were able to learn the operation of the CDIO syllabus.

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